

Gender Gaps and Technological Innovation: A Study on Women Professionals in the Agricultural Sector of Northern Celaya, Guanajuato

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ABSTRACT

This work analyzes two main dimensions: gender disparities and technological innovation, from a gender perspective. Data obtained through a study conducted with women professionals in the agricultural sector in the northern region of the municipality of Celaya, Guanajuato, are examined. The purpose was to make their contribution to sustainable agricultural innovation visible, identifying obstacles and opportunities, and proposing specific actions with a gender perspective.

INTRODUCTION

Gender constitutes an integrated social construct that assigns differentiated roles, responsibilities, and expectations based on sexual distinctions. An illustrative case is the assignment of male and female roles based on the sexual division of productive and reproductive work. This system imposes stereotypes and personality attributes for each gender, delimiting spaces for the development of activities and interests, and establishing hierarchies of social valuation. Traditionally, men have been associated with external and public activities – work, politics – and women with internal spheres such as domestic life, reproduction, and care for others (World Health Organization, 2018).

This research assesses the working conditions and quality of life of professional women working in agricultural-productive systems, evaluating their impact on processes aimed at sustainable agricultural innovation with a gender perspective. The study area comprises the northern zone of the municipality of Celaya, Guanajuato, which occupies 1.81% of the state's surface. This region includes 36 localities, from San Miguel Octopan to San Cayetano, within a municipality that has 417 localities and a total population of 468,469 inhabitants (Government of Guanajuato, 2024).

The northern zone of Celaya borders the municipalities of Santa Cruz de Juventino Rosas and Comonfort. It presents areas with slope instability, such as in the locality of Rincón

de Tamayo, at the top of Cerro Pelón. The region is characterized by scarps with north and east orientation, covering an area of 553.23 square kilometers. The predominant climate is semi-dry and semi-warm. The analysis focuses on the socioeconomic environment of the 2020-2024 period, examining the sociocultural framework that influences women's behavior through roles, prejudices, and factors that promote discrimination and unequal treatment, using a sustainable evaluation model.

DEVELOPMENT

In 2020, 35.4% of Guanajuato's population was in a situation of moderate poverty and 5.07% in extreme poverty. The population vulnerable due to social deprivations reached 25.9%, while the population vulnerable due to income was 10.4% (INEGI, 2020). In Celaya, the main social deprivations in 2020 were access to social security, access to health services, and access to food.

In recent years, women have operated in a different context, achieving a significant place in companies, organizations, and social roles. The state's economic growth, distributed uniformly, had the primary sector as its main component. This sector is composed of manufacturing industry, commercial activity, real estate and rental services, and finally the food industry (Economy, 2024).

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Celaya has a population of 268,124 women. The age ranges with the highest concentration were 15 to 19 years (44,962 inhabitants), 20 to 24 years (44,893 inhabitants), and 10 to 14 years (43,659 inhabitants), which together represent 25.6% of the total population. The median age of women is 30 years, compared to 28 years for men. Regarding the representation of mothers, single mothers constitute 27.6% (11,685 women), followed by separated mothers at 24.4% (10,295 women). The smallest group consists of divorced mothers, at 15.2% (6,426 women aged 12 and over) (Economy, 2024).

The above justifies the importance of having a situational socioeconomic diagnosis of the regional environment in the productive and agricultural service sectors, as well as the processes aimed at sustainable agricultural innovation with a gender perspective in northern Celaya (Data México, 2023). Sustainable agricultural innovation involves the development of advances in productive and agricultural service sectors that incorporate a gender perspective to improve design, creation, installation, operation, and to strengthen education, health, work, culture, and policy for the population. Some relevant areas include:

- Management of chemical fertilizers.
- Use of natural fertilizers applied with machinery.
- Marketing of basic grains such as corn, wheat, beans, rice, and sorghum.
- Labor in production units and sowing of grains or vegetables.
- Management of livestock breeding and production units (bovine, porcine, caprine, ovine, poultry), including deworming, vaccination, use of balanced feed, and sanitary control.
- Soil management with irrigation systems (gravity or rolling) or earthen channels.
- Day labor (temporary and family) in agricultural activities, with short or long-term shifts.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The study began with the characterization of the research subjects using predetermined variables. In this first stage, techniques for capturing information on the aforementioned

1. Sociodemographic Profile.

Table 1. Sociodemographic Profile

Characteristic	Data
Average Age	28 Years
Marital status	50% Single
Number of Children	70% Have at least one child
Educational level	60% Hold a bachelor's degree
Specialty	60% Have an Engineering degree related to Agriculture

production systems were employed, using semi-structured questionnaires, discussion groups, and in-depth interviews. The research team gathered information through observation when participants did not agree to be recorded.

In parallel, surveys were applied to women to evaluate their level of growth and development in daily life and, specifically, in their activities within the productive chain. A non-experimental mixed research approach (qualitative and quantitative) was adopted, conducting probabilistic sampling. Three hundred surveys were distributed across five companies in the primary and secondary sectors. The instruments (semi-structured questionnaires, discussion groups, interviews) were designed to be applied to women professionals in the agricultural sector in northern Celaya, in line with the 2030 Agenda (gob.mx, 2025).

Objective

To analyze and diagnose the working conditions and quality of life of professional women working in selected agricultural-productive systems, considering variables aligned with Sustainable Development Goal 5 (SDG, 2024) in the northern zone of Celaya, Guanajuato.

Hypothesis

It is proposed that there are two types of gaps in Agricultural Production Systems: those related to the gender perspective, manifested in the working conditions and quality of life of women professionals in the agricultural sector in northern Celaya, Guanajuato.

Variables

Nine topics were evaluated: I. Current per capita income. II. Educational lag. III. Access to health services. IV. Access to social security. V. Quality and space of housing. VI. Access to basic services in housing. VII. Access to nutritious and quality food. VIII. Degree of social cohesion and community integration. IX. Degree of accessibility to paved roads.

DISCUSSION AND ANALYSIS OF RESULTS

The results of the 300 applied surveys are explained in six aspects considering the nine previous topics, to elucidate the existing gender and technological innovation gaps.

Figure 1. Average marital status of professional women in the northern area of the municipality of Celaya.

Figure 2. Average education level of women in the northern area of the municipality of Celaya

Figure 3. Average specialization of professional women in the northern area of the municipality of Celaya

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According to the data, professional women in northern Celaya present a young profile, with solid academic training but limited participation in innovative practices.

2. Work Activities.

Table 2. Agricultural Practices.

Activities related to the agricultural innovation gap	Porcentaje
Activity 1. Various activities in agriculture	61.42 %
Activity 2. Technical or innovation activities in the use of fertilizers	8.00 %
Activity 3. Technical or innovation activities in production and sowing by area	10.00%
Activity 4. Technical or innovation activities in animal breeding and exploitation	8%.00
Activity 5. Technical or innovation activities in up-to-date knowledge in agriculture	6.33%
Activity 6. Technical or innovation activities and knowledge in irrigation systems	6.25%

Figure 4. Average specialization of professional women in the northern area of the municipality of Celaya

The data shows a significant gap in active participation in innovative agricultural practices, as only 38.58% of women are directly involved in technical or innovation activities.

3. Working Conditions.

Table 3. Working Conditions

Gap in working conditions	Percentage
Nutrition (rarely eats three meals a day)	40.00 %
Has not suffered labor discrimination	83.33%.
Has had pains or discomfort in the last 30 days	41.77%
Has suffered episodes of anxiety/depression	33.30%

Figure 5. Percentage of women who have suffered some type of health problem due to working conditions.

Figure 6. Percentage of women who have suffered some type of workplace discrimination.

Although only 41.7% directly associate their health problems with working conditions, the majority report low or no exposure to physical or chemical occupational risks, performing predominantly sedentary activities or with limited movement.

4. Infrastructure and Environment (Housing).

Figure 7. Main problems in housing and social environment.

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82.45% of professional women in the agricultural sector in northern Celaya do not report severe deficiencies in the evaluated housing aspects.

5. Innovation and Technology.

Table 4. Necessary Resources and Training

Training need	PERCENTAGE
Considers internet management and technology training necessary	33.30%
Considers training in drones and autonomous vehicles necessary.	33.30%.
Demands resources allocated for their research	33.40%

Figure 8. Type of training that women consider a priority.

An explicit demand for more training and more resources for research is observed. Although they have solid academic training, their participation in innovative practices is limited.

6. Gender Perspective and Social Participation.

Table 5. Perspective and Participation

Aspect of participation and perception	PERCENTAGE
Believes solidarity exists occasionally or rarely.	50.00%
Shows occasional interest in social participation and political news	41.70%.
Believes most people would try to take advantage of them	41.70%

Figure 9. Gender perspective.

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The majority opinion is that greater participation policies with gender equity are required to reduce gaps in technological innovation and to increase trust in governmental institutions.

CONCLUSIONS

Based on the data analysis, two central axes for action are highlighted:

The first refers to the need to break gender gaps in technological innovation through specialized technical and technological training, along with state-of-the-art equipment. It is crucial to strengthen training programs in precision agriculture, drone use, and Information and Communication Technologies (ICT), providing resources such as internet access, vehicles, and mobile devices.

This must be complemented by improving occupational health, implementing risk prevention and mental health programs. It is essential to promote work-life balance through supports such as daycare, flexible hours, and nutrition programs. Furthermore, networks of women farmers and dialogue spaces with a gender perspective should be promoted.

The second aspect involves addressing the gap in social participation. This can be achieved by strengthening technological training in collaboration with institutions such as SADER and SDAyR. Mental health programs should be implemented with the support of IMUG and INMUJERES.

Promoting collaborative networks among women farmers for knowledge exchange, and integrating the gender perspective into rural development and financing programs is necessary. Improving basic infrastructure and security, in coordination with the municipal government, is also a priority.

In summary, the professional women of Celaya are a key actor for sustainable agricultural innovation, but they face barriers related to technological training, mental health, and working conditions. Articulation between the three levels of government and civil society is essential to enhance their impact.

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